

Learning Interpretable Classifiers for PDDL Planning NP-hardness proof

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Abstract. This document contains the proof of NP-hardness of the problem we tackle in the main article. In this document, we show that with our construction, a negative Set Cover instance results in a negative \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning instance. The rest of the proof is, in essence, the same as in the main article.

1 The \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning problem

1.1 Problem definition

In this section, we introduce the main problem we are tackling in this paper.

Score function Our problem takes in input a *score function*, which associated a score $\sigma(\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle) \in \mathbb{R}$ to each trace. We say that an instantiated trace $\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle$ is *positive* iff $\sigma(\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle) \geq 0$. Otherwise, the instantiated trace is said to be *negative*.

In the following, we use $[\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle \models \psi]$ as a shorthand for the function equal to 1 if $\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle \models \psi$ and equal to 0 otherwise. The score function generalizes to formulas $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{FTL}$ as follows:

$$\sigma^T(\psi) = \sum_{\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle \in T} \sigma(\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle) [\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle \models \psi]$$

Problem 1. \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning

Input: \mathcal{D} a domain
 T a set of instantiated traces
 $r \in \mathbb{N}$ the maximum number of logical operators in the output formula
 $q \in \mathbb{N}$ the maximum number of quantifiers
 $\sigma : T \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a function called the score function

Output: A formula $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{FTL}$ such that ψ has at most r logical operators, and q quantifiers, and $\sum_{\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle \in T} \sigma(\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle) [\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle \models \psi]$ is maximal

1.2 Complexity

The decision problem associated to the \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning problem is the problem for which the output is *Yes* iff there exists a formula $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{FTL}$ satisfying the requirements above, and with score $\sigma^T(\psi) \geq \ell$, where ℓ is given in input.

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Proposition 1. *The decision problem associated to the \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning problem is NP-hard*

To show this result, we start by introducing the NP-hard problem we reduce to ours.

Problem 2. Set Cover

Input: A set $U = \{1, \dots, n\}$
A set S of subsets: $S = \{S_1, \dots, S_m\} \subseteq 2^U$
 $k \in \mathbb{N}$

Output: *Yes* iff there exists a subset $T \subseteq S$ such that $|T| \leq k$ and $\cup_{s \in T} s = U$
No otherwise

Proof of Proposition 1. Using the notation above, let us consider an instance of *Set Cover*. We build an instance of \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning that is positive (i.e. outputs *Yes*) iff the *Set Cover* instance is positive.

The proof consists in showing that a set of positive traces can be described by a formula \mathcal{L}_{FTL} satisfying the constraints in input iff there exists a set cover of size at most k . Each of the positive traces is associated to an element j of U , and contains a single state (and thus, temporal modalities have no effect). This single state carries the information as to which subsets contain j . The information consists of fluents of the form $\text{in}(S_i)$. For instance, if the j -th trace is $\{\langle \text{in}(S_1), \text{in}(S_3) \rangle\}$, then only sets $S_1, S_3 \in S$ contain element $j \in U$.

Each subset S_i of S , in the *Set Cover* instance given in input, is associated a unique type Set_i in the PDDL domain we build. As our \mathcal{L}_{FTL} formulas quantify on these types, and since we restrict the number of quantifiers to $q = k$, any output formula of the \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning problem can only reason on at most k subsets among those in S . If k quantifiers are enough to distinguish between the positive traces (associated to elements $j \in U$) and a mock trace, then k subsets are enough to cover all elements of U . Otherwise, no set cover of size at most k exists.

More formally, let us define the input of our \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning instance as follows: the shared domain is $\mathcal{D} = \langle \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{T} \rangle$, where the set of types is $\mathcal{T} = \{\text{Set}_1, \dots, \text{Set}_m, \text{Set}\}$, $\mathcal{P} = \{\text{in}\}$ (with $\text{ar}(\text{in}) = 1$ and $\tau_{\text{in}}(1) = \text{Set}$), and $\mathcal{A} = \emptyset$ (since all traces have length 1, no action is needed).

Each instantiated trace is associated its own instance, which is in turn associated to a unique element $j \in U$: for $j \leq n$, $\mathcal{I}_j = \langle \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{H}, I_j, G_j \rangle$. The shared set of objects contains the sets of the *Set Cover* input instance, and is such that $\mathcal{O} = \{S_1, \dots, S_m, d\}$ (where

d is a mock object that we use to discriminate traces later). The type hierarchy $\mathcal{H} = \{\{S_i\} \mid S_i \in S\} \cup \mathcal{O}$ associates each set to its own unique type in our PDDL domain: types are such that $\tau(S_i) = \text{Set}_i$ for all $i \leq m$, and $\tau(\mathcal{O}) = \text{Set}$. The information regarding which sets j belongs to is encoded in the initial state and goal of \mathcal{I}_j : for $j \leq n$, $\mathcal{I}_j = G_j = \{\text{in}(S_i) \mid j \in S_i\}$.

We also define a mock, negative instance $\mathcal{I}_d = \langle \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{H}, I_d, G_d \rangle$, with $I_d = \{\text{in}(d)\}$, and $G_d = I_d$. We have $T = \{\langle t_j, \mathcal{I}_j \rangle \mid j \leq n\} \cup \{\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle\}$, where $t_j = \langle \mathcal{I}_j \rangle$ and $t_d = \langle I_d \rangle$. We set $r = m - 1$, $q = k$, and the score $\sigma(\langle t_j, \mathcal{I}_j \rangle)$ of every trace to 1, except $\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle$ for which $\sigma(\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle) = -1$. The decision problem consists in finding whether there exists a formula $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{FTL}}$ that can that is satisfied by every trace, except $\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle$. Thus, the score threshold we set is $\ell = m$. Let us now show that this instance is positive iff our *Set Cover* instance is positive.

Suppose that there exists a set cover $T = \{S_{i_1}, \dots, S_{i_k}\}$. Then there exists a formula $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{FTL}}$ with score exactly m :

$$\psi := \exists x_1 \in \text{Set}_{i_1}, \dots, \exists x_k \in \text{Set}_{i_k}. \bigvee_{j \leq k} \text{in}(x_j)$$

We have that $\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle \not\models \psi$, but all other traces satisfy ψ , since T is a set cover. So the formula has score exactly m , and is a positive instance of \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning.

Now suppose that there exists no set cover of size at most k for the input instance. By contradiction, suppose that there exists a formula ψ with score m (which is the maximum possible score). We denote T' the set of types on which ψ quantifies upon. We have that $|T'| \leq k$.

Since there exists no set cover of size at most k , then there exists $w \leq n$ such that $w \notin \cup_{s \in T'} s$. We proceed to show that if $\langle t_w, \mathcal{I}_w \rangle \models \psi$, then $\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle \models \psi$, which contradicts the fact that ψ has score m .

Since all instances share the same set of objects (and the same environments), in the rest of this proof, we denote $t, e \models \psi$ as a shorthand for $\langle t, \mathcal{I} \rangle, e \models \psi$. We introduce two lemmas, which are stronger results than needed here, but that are necessary for the proof. Let $C_w = \{o \in \mathcal{O} \mid \text{in}(o) \in I_w\}$, $C_d = \{d\}$, $\overline{C_w} = \mathcal{O} \setminus C_w$, and $\overline{C_d} = \mathcal{O} \setminus C_d$.

Lemma 2. *Let $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{FTL}}$, $v \in \{d, w\}$, and $v' \in \{d, w\} \setminus \{v\}$. If there exists an environment e s.t. $t_v, e \models \psi$, then there exists an environment e' s.t. $t_{v'}, e' \models \psi$, and e' is such that for every $x \in \mathcal{X}$ s.t. $x[e] \in C_v$ (resp. $\overline{C_v}$), we have $x[e'] \in C_{v'}$ (resp. $\overline{C_{v'}}$)*

In the following lemma, for $v \in \{d, w\}$, we say that two environments e and e' are *indistinguishable for C_v* if, for every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, $x[e] \in C_v$ iff $x[e'] \in C_v$ (and thus, $x[e] \in \overline{C_v}$ iff $x[e'] \in \overline{C_v}$).

Lemma 3. *Let $\psi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{FTL}}$, $v \in \{d, w\}$. Suppose that there exists an environment e s.t. $t_v, e \models \psi$. Then for every environment e' such that e and e' are indistinguishable for C_v , we have $t_v, e' \models \psi$.*

Intuitively, these lemmas translate the fact that trace t_w (resp. t_d) can not distinguish two objects that occur in I_w (resp. I_d), and that objects of C_w (resp. $\overline{C_w}$) that occur in an environment e that satisfies ψ with t_w can be replaced by objects of C_d (resp. $\overline{C_d}$) to create a new environment e' , so that ψ is satisfied by t_d with e' .

We prove both lemmas simultaneously, by induction over the structure of ψ . We only show the cases where $v = w$, although the cases where $v = d$ are shown analogously. We start by proving by induction that these lemmas hold when $\psi = \varphi \in \mathcal{L}_{\text{TL}}$.

The case $\varphi = \text{in}(x)$ is immediate, by construction.

Suppose that $\varphi = \neg\varphi'$. (Lemma 2) Suppose that there exists e s.t. $t_w, e \models \varphi$. Then $t_w, e \not\models \varphi'$, and there exists e' such that $t_d, e' \not\models \varphi'$ (which is something that we obtain by using the induction hypothesis of both lemmas). So $t_d, e' \models \varphi$. The converse is shown in a similar way. (Lemma 3) Suppose that $t_w, e \models \varphi$. Then $t_w, e \not\models \varphi'$, and for every environment e' such that e and e' are indistinguishable for C_w , $t_w, e' \not\models \varphi'$ (by induction hypothesis). So $t_w, e' \models \varphi$.

Suppose that $\varphi = \varphi_1 \wedge \varphi_2$. (Lemma 2) Suppose that there exists e such that $t_w, e \models \varphi$. By induction hypothesis, there exists e'_1 and e'_2 such that $t_d, e'_1 \models \varphi_1$ and $t_d, e'_2 \models \varphi_2$. Using the induction hypothesis of Lemma 3, we have that (since e'_1 and e'_2 are indistinguishable for C_d) there exists e' an environment such that $t_d, e' \models \varphi_1$ and $t_d, e' \models \varphi_2$, so $t_d, e' \models \varphi$. Showing that the induction hypothesis of Lemma 3 carries over is straightforward.

The cases of temporal modalities are immediate, since all traces have length 1.

Suppose that $\psi = \exists x \in E. \psi'$, where $E \in \mathcal{T}$. Now suppose that $E = \text{Set}_i$ for some i (the proof when $E = \text{Set}$ is similar). (Lemma 2) Suppose that there exists e such that $t_w, e \models \psi$. Then there exists $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $\tau(o) = \text{Set}_i$ such that $t_w, e[x := o] \models \psi$. Note that $o \in \overline{C_w}$ (by hypothesis on t_w , since w is not covered by the set of subsets T' on which ψ quantifies upon). There exists $o' \in \overline{C_d}$ and an environment e' such that $t_w, e'[x := o'] \models \psi'$. Since $o \in \overline{C_d}$, Lemma 3 ensures that $t_w, e'[x := o] \models \psi$. So $t_w, e' \models \psi$. Lemma 3 is proven in a similar way, since by induction hypothesis, any environment e'' indistinguishable with e' for C_d .

Suppose that $\psi = \forall x \in E. \psi'$, where $E \in \mathcal{T}$. Since there exists a unique $o \in \mathcal{O}$ such that $\tau(o) = \text{Set}_i$ for all i , the case $E = \text{Set}_i$ can be shown in the same way as above. Now suppose that $E = \text{Set}$, and that there exists an environment e such that $t_w, e \models \psi$. For all $o \in \mathcal{O}$, $t_w, e[x := o] \models \psi'$. Let $o_1 \in C_w$ and $o_2 \in \overline{C_w}$. Then by induction hypothesis, there exist e'_1, e'_2 two environments, $o'_1 \in C_d$ and $o'_2 \in \overline{C_d}$ such that $t_d, e'_1[x := o'_1] \models \psi'$ and $t_d, e'_2[x := o'_2] \models \psi'$. Since e'_1 and e'_2 are indistinguishable for C_d , and by induction hypothesis, we have that $t_d, e'_1[x := o'_1] \models \psi'$ and $t_d, e'_1[x := o'_2] \models \psi'$. Since, for any $o''_1 \in C_d$ (and $o''_2 \in \overline{C_d}$), $e'_1[x := o''_1]$ and $e'_1[x := o''_1]$ are indistinguishable for C_d (as well as $e'_1[x := o''_2]$ and $e'_1[x := o''_2]$), we have that, for any $o'' \in \mathcal{O}$, $t_d, e'_1[x := o''] \models \psi'$. Hence, $t_d, e'_1 \models \psi'$. Since any other environment e'' indistinguishable with e'_1 over C_d could have been chosen, Lemma 3 also holds.

This concludes the proof of both lemmas. An immediate corollary of Lemma 2 is that $\langle t_w, \mathcal{I}_w \rangle \models \psi$ iff $\langle t_d, \mathcal{I}_d \rangle \models \psi$. As a consequence, $\sigma^T(\psi) < m$, which is a contradiction with ψ being a solution to our \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning instance.

As such, the \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning instance we built is positive iff the set cover instance is positive. As a consequence, the \mathcal{L}_{FTL} learning problem is NP-hard. \square